

Proceedings of the meeting of Board of Studies in Hotel Management held on 2nd April 2017,
11 a.m at college conference hall, Srinivas University, Mangalore.

Members Present

1. Prof. Anet Florence
2. Mr. Swaminathan S
3. Mr. Sourabh Samaddar

Members Absent

1. Mr. Rajesh Kumar
2. Mr. Naren Thimmaiah

The chairperson of the BOS in Hotel Management welcomed all the members present and briefed the purpose & agenda of the meeting.

**Agenda -1 Introduction of under graduate programmes in Hotel Management,
Preparation of the detailed curriculum, scheme of instruction & scheme of examination.**

The chairperson explained briefly about the establishment of Srinivas University and the programmes being introduced under Srinivas University. She said it is proposed to introduce 2 undergraduate programmes under Srinivas University College of Hotel Management & Tourism namely Bachelor of Hotel Management & Catering Technology (BHMCT) - 4 Years & B.Sc(Hotel Management) - 3 Years. She provided the draft syllabus of the said programmes prepared by the faculty of Srinivas University. She explained the commitment of the University in adopting CBCS -CAGP pattern of education and gave an overview of Srinivas University Regulations for UG Programmes and requested the board to discuss on the issue & take appropriate decision & help the University to start the said programmes from the academic year 2017 -18. The BOS members discussed the agenda in detail & drafted the course curriculum including the scheme of instruction, eligibility criteria, etc. for BHMCT & B.Sc(HM) programmes & resolved as under .

Resolution: The Board unanimously resolved to recommend to the University to introduce BHMCT & B.Sc(HM) programmes in Srinivas University from the Academic year 2017-18. The Board also recommended to adopt the scheme of instruction, scheme of examination & detailed curriculum for BHMCT & B.Sc(HM) courses drafted as per CBCS & CAGP regulations (Annexure - I,II & III).

Agenda: 2 Preparation of scheme of examination and pattern of Question paper.

The Chairperson explained the guidelines relating to scheme of examination/and pattern of question paper & requested the Board to work out the scheme of examination and decide about the pattern of question papers to be adopted for the said programmes. Accordingly the Board went through the guidelines of the scheme of examination provided to the Board & prepared the detailed scheme of examination and pattern of question papers for BHMCT & B.Sc(HM) & resolved as under

Resolution: The Board resolved to recommend to the University to accept the pattern of question papers prepare by this Board of Studies for BHMCT & B.Sc(HM) & to adopt the same in Srinivas University from the academic year 2017-18.

Agenda - 3 : Preparation of Panel of Examiners

The chairperson requested the Board Members to prepare the panel of examiners for the 1st & 2nd semester end examination for the BHMCT & B.Sc(HM) programmes.

Resolution : The board prepared the panel of examiners (Internal & External) for the 1st & 2nd semester end examination for the BHMCT & B.Sc(HM) programmes & resolved to recommend the same to the University. (The panel of examiners is sent separately in a sealed cover to the Registrar (Evaluation)).

Agenda - 4: Any other matter with the permission of the chair person.

The Board discussed on various issues related to imparting BHMCT & B.Sc(HM) programmes & resolved to recommend as under:

1. BOS Members recommended introducing Industrial Training (internship) in 6th semester.
2. BOS Members recommended introducing seminars & mini projects in all semesters.
3. BOS Members recommended giving flexibility to select soft core subjects & also give scope for fast learners.
4. BOS Members recommended reducing class room teaching & increasing practical component in curriculum.

At the end, the chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Prof. Anet Florence

Chairperson

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Proceedings of the meeting of the Board of Studies in Hotel Management held on 13th of November 2019, 2.00p.m at college Meeting room, Srinivas University, Mangalore.

Members Present

1. Prof. Swaminathan S
2. Mr.Padmanabha K.
3. Mr. Sreejith O. V.

Members Absent

1. Mr. Rajesh Kumar – represented by Mr Subrat Saraf
2. Mr. Naren Thimmaiah – represented by Mr. Prashanth Prabhu

The chairperson of the BOS in Hotel Management welcomed all the members present. He explained the agenda of the meeting in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

Agenda 1: Revision of curriculum of “F & B Production” pertaining to BHMCT and B.Sc.HM

Mr.Sreejith presented following changes in the curriculum of F & B Production of BHMCT and B.Sc.HM different semesters:

1. It was proposed that Unit 4 of 17/HM4/13 and 17/HM3/13 be shifted to 17/HM4/23 and 17/HM3/23 as Unit 1. This would ensure that students receive the concepts of the subject step by step.
2. It was proposed that the curriculum content of F & B Production Practical I – BHMCT and B.Sc.HM be exchanged with the content of F & B Production Practical II – BHMCT & B.Sc.HM. This would ensure streamlined learning experience in support of corresponding theory curriculum.
3. It was proposed that Unit 1 and Unit 2 of 17/HM4/41 AND 17/HM3/41 be combined while scrapping off the topics Haryana, Uttarakhand and Himachal Pradesh. Thus Unit 3 and 4 be Unit 2 and 3. This could be followed by incorporating Unit 3 from 17/HM4/51 and 17/HM3/51 into 17/HM4/41 AND 17/HM3/41 as Unit 4 (Indian sweets and desserts)
4. It was proposed that Karnataka Cuisine be incorporated into the renamed Unit 3 of 17/HM4/41 AND 17/HM3/41 and the Unit 3 be renamed as “Cuisines of Karnataka Maharashtra and Goa”
5. It was proposed that two menus of Karnataka cuisine be included by replacing them with the menus of Himachal Pradesh and Uttarakhand in the practical curriculum of BHMCT/ B.Sc.HM IV Semester.
6. It was proposed that the concept of basic baking be incorporated in the curriculum of 17/HM4/51 and 17/HM3/51 as Unit 3 (Basic Baking)
7. In Menu No. 7 of F and B Production Practicals BHMCT/ B.Sc.HM, one savoury item (Idiyappam) be replaced by a sweet preparation (ILA ADA)

All changes are mentioned in the attached annexure

Resolution – It was resolved to send all proposed changes to the Registrar Evaluation for subsequent execution in the new curriculum

Agenda II : Revision of curriculum of “Accommodation and front office operations” pertaining to BHMCT and B.Sc.HM

Mr Subrat Saraf after due consultation with the industry representatives presented the following proposals in the curriculum of Accommodation and Front office operations of BHMCT and B.Sc.HM different semesters:

1. It was proposed that the topic "Types and classifications of hotels on different basis, star categorization, heritage hotels and others in India, organization structure of hotels" be scrapped off from Unit 1 of 17/HM4/14 and 17/HM3/14, as similar topics exist in the course 17/HM4/17 and 17/HM3/17. Also, to scrap off "Guest safety on floors, guest safety procedures during fire emergency" from Unit 2 in 17/HM4/14 and 17/HM3/14 as topics are not into basic level and already exist in the senior level semesters.
2. It was proposed that topics be added in the curriculum of 17/HM4/14 and 17/HM3/14 as shown:

CHAPTER-NAME	ADDITIONS
Accommodation sector	Special features of high end hotels globally – sauna, Jacuzzi, spa, etc
Guest accommodation	Virtual Reality concept, linen classification
Hotel front office	Atrium

The above mentioned topics are in trend in the industry and most important to be learnt.

3. It was proposed that topics be added in the curriculum of 17/HM4/24 and 17/HM3/24 as shown:

CHAPTER-NAME	ADDITIONS
Cleaning science	Litmus paper test, dispensing of cleaning agents
Housekeeping procedures and routines	Duty Rota, biometric locking unlocking, inventories – types and associated budgets
The front office – reservations and arrival	Business seasons
The guest room servicing	Bringing pantry at par, room cleaning preferences, second services, closing down – concept of linen chute

4. It was proposed that topics be added in the curriculum of 17/HM4/32 and 17/HM3/32 as shown:

CHAPTER-NAME	ADDITIONS
Cleaning and upkeep of public areas and supervision	Thresh hold levels, role of a floor supervisor in rooms
Special provisions, safety and security	Occupational hazards, potential hazards in housekeeping, Laws, security equipment in brief, fire safety
The front office – guest stay	Modes of payment, GRE, yield and ARR
Front office accounting, departure and post departure services	Establishing credit line, credit card, software used in hotels (brief)

5. Other reshuffling/renaming of contents of curriculum of the subject based on streamlining the subject knowledge of students and teaching-learning process was proposed

(Annexure attached – Page number 7 to 11 – new content)

Resolution – It was resolved to send all proposed changes to the Registrar Evaluation for subsequent execution in the new curriculum

Agenda III: . Revision of curriculum of “Introduction to hospitality” pertaining to BHMCT and B.Sc.HM

Mr Subrat Saraf presented that topic “Hotel guest, Different types of hotel rooms” be scrapped off from Unit 3 of 17/HM4/17 AND 17/HM3/17 as same topic exists in the curriculum of 17/HM4/14 and 17/HM3/14.

(Annexure attached)

Resolution – It was resolved to send all proposed changes to the Registrar Evaluation for subsequent execution in the new curriculum

All proposals given were accepted by the chairperson and finalized to be sent to the University for approval and implementation. BHMCT-Total modifications are done 12 Percentage of Modifications 21% B.Sc-HM Total modifications are done 10 Percentage of Modifications 24% In the end, the chairperson thanked everyone for being present for the meeting and for their valuable suggestions.

1. Prof.Swaminathan
Chairperson
BOS in Hotel Management

Dean
College of Hotel Management & Tourism
Srinivas University
Srinivas Campus
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru - 575001

2. Mr.Padmanabha K
Member
BOS in Hotel Management
3. Mr.Sreejith O.V
Member
BOS in Hotel Management

4. Mr.Subrat Saraf
Representative

5. Mr.Prasanth Prabhu
Representative

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MINUTES OF THE BOS MEETING HELD ON 18 MARCH 2020

MEMBERS PRESENT

1. PROF. SWAMINATHAN S
2. PROF. PADMANABHA K
3. PROF. SREEJITH O V
4. PROF. SUBRAT SARAF
5. PROF. PRASHANTH PRABHU

VENUE: DEAN'S CHAMBER
TIME: 4.15 PM

THE BOS MEETING WAS CONDUCTED IN ORDER TO DISCUSS ABOUT THE FOLLOWING AGENDA

1. ADDING ONE MORE TRAINING SESSION FOR A SEMESTER
2. INTRODUCTION OF NEW COURSE – B.SC-HM AVIATION, TRAVEL & TOURISM
3. CHANGE IN SYLLABUS PATTERN

Agenda: 1 Prof. Swaminathan proposed that the pattern of BHMCT need to be changed and the students should be provided with additional training for on semester. The advantage of this system is that the students will get more exposure in the specialized area, especially the students belonging to the eighth semester. The initial training in the Fifth semester will be called Industrial Exposure Training and the second training in Eighth semester will be On the Job Training. Prof Padmanabha backed this suggestion.

Agenda:2 Prof. Swaminathan proposed that a new course B.SC-HM with AVIATION, TRAVEL & TOURISM may be added as per the suggestion from Management. The following were the subjects suggested for the same. Airline Industry – Introduction, Aviation Law and Aircraft Rules and Regulation, Transportation, Safety and Security, Principles of Airport Management, Airline Catering Practical, Cabin Crew Service Practical, Bakery Practical

Agenda:3 The members suggested the following changes to be made in the syllabus

1. The syllabus of third, fourth and fifth semesters need to be combined and distributed in Third and Fourth semesters respectively for Food & Beverage Service and Food Production(Theory & Practical)
2. Regular B.SC-HM students will have the following subjects – F&B Service(T). F&B Production(T), Event Management, Hotel Law, Economics, Hotel Marketing, Mixology(p), Bakery (p).
3. – F&B Service(Theory and Practical) to be added instead of Introduction to Hospitality in the First semester of BHMCT and B.SC-HM. By adding the Practical, the students Credits will be increased. BHMCT -Total modifications done 13,Percentage of Modifications 23%
B.sc-HM Total modifications are done 14, Percentage of Modifications 28%

Members Present

1. Prof. Swaminathan S (Chairperson)
2. Prof Padmanabha K
3. Mr. Sreejith O. V.
4. Mr. Subrat Saraf
5. Mr. Prashanth Prabhu

Dean
Prof. Swaminathan S
Chairperson
BOS in Hotel Management

Proceedings of the meeting of the Board of Studies in Hotel Management held on 20th of November 2021, 2.00p.m at college Meeting room, Srinivas University, Mangalore.

Members Present

1. Prof. Swaminathan S
2. Prof Padmanabha P.
3. Mr. Sreejith O. V.

Members Absent

1. Mr. Rajesh Kumar – represented by Mr Subrat Saraf
2. Mr. Naren Thimmaiah – represented by Mr. Prashant Prabhu

The chairperson of the BOS in Hotel Management welcomed all the members present. He explained the agenda of the meeting in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

Agenda I- Execution of industrial training for VI ,& VII sem

Mr Sreejith O V, Member, proposed to commence the Industrial training for VI sem BHMCT/BSCHM & VII sem BHMCT from 13th of December with a cushion gap of 10 days tentatively between their last exam and commencement of training program. As decided in the previous BOS meeting, the students of forthcoming VIII sem BHMCT were also covered under the training programme. The proposal was accepted by Chairperson and instructions were given for implementation.

Agenda II- Implementation of New Education Policy 2021

Mr Swaminathan S, Chairperson proposed to implement NEP-2021 to current first year fresher students of BHMCT, BSC HM first semester, to which all the members agreed. According to the structure of NEP for courses under Hotel management related higher education sent by Government of Karnataka (HEC-Higher Education Council), the programme structure was discussed and framed (Annexure-I) and forwarded to the higher authorities of the University for approval. The syllabus change was 100% for all courses.

Members Present

1. Prof. Swaminathan S (Chairperson)
2. Prof Padmanabha K.
3. Mr. Sreejith O. V.
4. Mr. Subrat Saraf
5. Mr. Prashanth Prabhu

Prof. Swaminathan S
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